
OPTIMIZATION OF MOVING AVERAGE CROSSOVER STRATEGIES IN THE NEPAL STOCK EXCHANGE (NEPSE)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effectiveness of various Moving Averages (MA) trading algorithms, namely Simple Moving Average (SMA), Exponential Moving Average (EMA), and Triple Smoothed Exponential Moving Average (TSEMA), in the context of the Nepal Stock Exchange (NEPSE). Stocks were classified into three categories: High Cap, Mid Cap, and Low Cap, based on market capitalization. The optimal short- and long-term window parameters (n_1 , n_2) were determined using historical price data for each category. The algorithms were evaluated under both ideal and real-world conditions, the latter incorporating transaction costs and varying levels of investment capital (Rs.50,000 and Rs.1,00,00,000). Performance was assessed using multiple metrics, including average profit percentage, Sharpe ratio, maximum drawdown, and the average number of trades executed. Results indicate that TSEMA consistently outperforms SMA and EMA across most categories, offering superior returns and stability while maintaining lower trading frequency. Although the Buy & Hold strategy shows higher absolute returns in certain cases, MA-based strategies demonstrate improved risk-adjusted performance, particularly in volatile market segments. These findings suggest that adaptive MA-based trading frameworks such as TSEMA can provide viable, data-driven alternatives to passive investment strategies in emerging markets like Nepal.

Keywords: Moving Average Crossover, NEPSE, Technical Analysis, Algorithm Optimization, Emerging Market

1 Introduction

The application of technical analysis in financial markets has been a subject of both academic and practical interest. Among the various trading strategies analyzed and employed by traders and investors, the Moving Average (MA) crossover strategy is one of the simpler and widely used one. This strategy, which generates trading signals on the basis of crossing of two different moving averages (one lagging and the other forward moving), is a fundamental tool for identifying and predicting the market trends. Despite its popularity, the effectiveness of the MA crossover strategy is highly sensitive to the specific parameters as well as the underlying market conditions, making its profitability a subject of continuous optimization and analysis.

While extensive research has been conducted on the performance of technical trading strategies including the MA crossover strategy in mature markets like that of the United States and BRICS nation (de Souza, Ramos, Pena, Sobreiro, & Kimura, 2018) (Ikhlaas, 2016)), there is a notable scarcity of similar empirical studies focusing on emerging markets such as of Nepal. The Nepal Stock Exchange (NEPSE), as a developing and relatively slow market, presents unique

characteristics such as low liquidity, high volatility and different regulatory frameworks, which can significantly influence the performance of the MA crossover strategy. This study seeks to address this significant gap.

The primary objective of this paper is to evaluate the optimal moving average and time period for the MA crossover strategy in the context of NEPSE to yield the highest returns over a historical period. Furthermore, we will critically evaluate the profitability and risk-adjusted returns of the optimized strategy against a conventional buy-and-hold approach, which serves as a standard benchmark. The findings of this research will not only move forward the academic knowledge on technical analysis on emerging markets but also provide actionable insights for participants in NEPSE.

To achieve this objective, we employed a back testing methodology on historical price data of stocks from the NEPSE. Our analysis spanned a comprehensive time period, allowing for a robust analysis and optimization of various MA parameter combinations. The primary findings indicate that among the tested algorithms, the Triple Smoothed Exponential Moving Average (TSEMA) strategy consistently outperformed both the Simple Moving Average (SMA) and Exponential Moving Average (EMA) approaches across most stock categories. Specifically, TSEMA exhibited superior performance in terms of average returns and Sharpe ratios, alongside lower trading frequency and drawdowns, highlighting its efficiency and stability even in the context of NEPSE's inherent market inefficiencies. Although the traditional Buy & Hold strategy occasionally achieved higher absolute returns, it did so with considerably higher volatility and risk exposure. These results suggest that properly optimized MA crossover strategies, particularly TSEMA-based models can offer more favorable risk-adjusted outcomes in emerging markets such as Nepal. Consequently, this study provides empirical evidence that adaptive technical trading frameworks can serve as practical tools for improving decision-making and enhancing portfolio performance in developing financial markets.

2 Literature Review

The foundation of modern technical analysis is rooted in the belief that historical price data can be used to predict future price movements. This principle has led to the development of numerous trading strategies, with the moving average (MA) crossover being one of the most widely used and studied. Academic literature on the efficiency of this strategy, however, presents mixed and often market specific findings.

Studies on large and mature markets such as the S&P500 have shown that the MA crossover strategy resulted in lower returns but also lower risk compared to buy-and-hold strategy (Ikhlās, 2016). On the other hand, the strategy shows positive results on emerging markets such as the Romanian Stock Market and the Malaysian Stock Market (Anghel, 2013) (Tapa, Yean, & Ahmad, 2016).

Despite this growing body of research, a significant gap exists in the literature regarding the application and optimization of such strategies in smaller, developing economies such as of Nepal. This is particularly relevant given findings that suggest these markets may exhibit a different form of behavior which influences the profitability of the MA crossover strategy. A recent study by Khanal et al. (Khanal, Thapa, & Bhandari, 2025), for instance, found that the Nepalese Stock Market, including its sectorial indices, is not efficient in the weak form. Their results indicated that future returns are predictable and that investors may be able to earn abnormal profits by using trading strategies that exploit these inefficiencies. These findings are in strong agreement with another recent study by Risal and Koju (Risal & Koju, 2021), which also concluded that the Nepalese stock market is inefficient in its weak form based on normality, autocorrelation, and run tests. These findings provide a compelling theoretical basis for our research.

This paper builds upon this existing research by focusing specifically on the moving average crossover strategy in the context of the Nepal Stock Exchange (NEPSE). By performing a focused optimization and analysis, we aim to provide a more definitive understanding of its potential profitability. This study's contribution is to fill the void of rigorous, empirical research on this specific strategy, offering a data-driven guide for investors in this unique and under-researched market.

3 Data and Methods

3.1 Data Source and Collection:

For the backtesting and optimization process, the study requires a historical dataset of daily Open, High, Low and Close (OHLC) prices for all listed stocks on the NEPSE. The primary data source for training and analyzing the trading bot will be the Sharehub API, accessible via the URL: <https://sharehubnepal.com/data/api/v1/candle-chart/history?symbol=CIT&resolution=1D&countback=0&isAdjust=true>. This API allows for fetching historical OHLC prices data for any stock and index by changing the "symbol" parameter in the URL. Similarly, sharesansar website is used for the data on the market capitalization of the stocks which is used to filter them.

The lookback period for each stock will begin from its listing date (with the oldest being 20-07-1998 for the NEPSE index) to 15-09-2025, excluding the first three trading weeks (15days) to avoid any potential skewing of results from initial listing gains and rise or vice versa when volume is generally very low. Furthermore, the historical adjusted price is used which accounts for all cooperate actions such as stock splits, Follow-on Public Offer (FPO) and bonus share distribution.

For the purpose of this study, NEPSE listed companies are categorized into three size tiers based on their market capitalization (total shares x price per share) as follows:

Table 1: Classification of the stocks listed in NEPSE

Type	Market Capitalization (in NPR)	Characteristics
Large Cap	More than 30 billion	Low volatility and growth potential but High liquidity
Mid Cap	5–30 billion	Moderate volatility and liquidity but High growth potential
Small Cap	Less than 5 billion	Very high volatility and growth potential but low liquidity

Note. The table provides an overview on the types of stocks listed in NEPSE on the basis of their size along with their major characteristics. The market capitalization is in Nepali Rupees (NPR) and as of 15-09-2025, 1 USD = 140.96 NPR.

Due to the varying characteristics of the different types of stocks, the algorithm is optimized and analyzed for each category individually to see if any of their unique character affects the parameter’s optimized value as well as the algorithm’s profitability.

On the other hand, since the NEPSE and the other sector indexes (such as BANKING, DEVBANK etc.) cannot be traded like stocks, they aren’t included in the dataset. Instead, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity is conducted on them.

3.2 Algorithmic Framework: Moving Averages

Since Moving Averages (MA) are the crux of the MA crossover strategy, the study evaluates five distinct moving averages, each with a unique mathematical formulation and weighting scheme. This allows for a comparative analysis of standard, well-established methods against custom, market-specific approaches. The MAs are discussed in brief below.

3.2.1 Simple Moving Average (SMA)

The Simple Moving Average (SMA) is the most straightforward of the technical indicators. It is calculated by taking the arithmetic mean of a series of prices over a defined lookback period, 'n'. The SMA gives equal weight to all data points within the period, regardless of their recency. The formula for the SMA at time 't' is:

$$SMA_t = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} P_{t-i}$$

Where P_{t-i} is the price on day $t - i$ and n is the lookback period in trading days. The value of lookback period n is subject to parameter optimization.

3.2.2 Exponential Moving Average (EMA)

In contrast to the SMA, the Exponential Moving Average (EMA) is a type of moving average that places a greater weight and significance on the most recent data points. This characteristic makes the EMA more responsive to current price changes than the SMA. The EMA is calculated iteratively, with each new EMA value incorporating the current price and the previous day’s EMA value. The formula for the EMA at time 't' is:

$$EMA_t = \alpha P_t + (1 - \alpha) EMA_{t-1}$$

where P_t is the current price, EMA_{t-1} is the previous EMA value, and α is the smoothing constant, which is a function of the lookback period n . A standard calculation for the smoothing constant is $\alpha = 2/(n + 1)$. This ensures that the EMA is appropriately weighted based on its lookback period.

3.2.3 Triple Smoothing Exponential Moving Average (TSEMA)

The TSEMA is a further refinement of the EMA strategy that applies the EMA three times in a nested fashion. This multiple smoothing is designed to reduce the lag that is inherent in single EMA calculations and to provide an even more responsive moving average that can more accurately track price movements. The formula for the TSEMA at time 't' is:

$$\text{TSEMA}_t = \text{EMA}_t(\text{EMA}_t(\text{EMA}_t(P_t)))$$

where P_t is the price and EMA_t is the EMA at time t.

3.3 Trade Execution and Performance Metrics:

The core of the backtesting methodology is the implementation of a crossover strategy using a "fast" moving average MA1 and a "slow" moving average MA2. The fast MA1, with a shorter lookback period n_1 , is intended to capture short-term trends and momentum. The slow MA2, with a longer lookback period n_2 , reflects the long-term trend of the market.

The trade signals are generated based on the following rules:

- Buy Signal: A buy order is executed when the fast MA (MA1) crosses above the slow MA (MA2). This event is considered a "bullish" crossover and indicates a potential upward price momentum.
- Sell Signal: A sell order is executed when the fast MA (MA1) crosses below the slow MA (MA2). This event is considered a "bearish" crossover and indicates a potential downward price momentum.

The lookback periods for the fast and slow MAs are not fixed. But due to the 3day transaction period of the Nepal Stock Exchange not allowing for intraday or Buy Today Sell Tomorrow (BTST), a lower limit of $n_1 \geq 5$ (equal to one trading week) is placed on the MA1 lookback period and minimum gap of 3 days is placed between a buy and sell signal. Similarly, since NEPSE doesn't allow short selling, it isn't considered.

Furthermore, to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the strategies' effectiveness, the study is moved beyond a simple analysis of net profit. A strategy with a high return but also an extremely high risk of loss is not practical. Therefore, a multi-faceted set of performance metrics is used to assess each strategy based on its returns, risk, and consistency.

The key metrics that are calculated and considered in the optimization process are:

- Profit%: The profit of the algorithm expressed in terms of percentage, providing a standardized measure of profitability.
- Annualized Sharpe Ratio (SR): A measure of risk-adjusted return, calculated by dividing the excess return over a risk-free rate by the strategy's volatility. A higher value means greater returns relative to the inherent risk. The formula is as follows

$$\text{SR} = \frac{\bar{R}_{daily}}{\sigma_{daily}} \sqrt{252}$$

where \bar{R}_{daily} is the average daily return and σ_{daily} is the standard deviation of daily return from the mean return also known as volatility.

- Maximum Drawdown: The largest peak-to-trough decline over the backtesting period, which indicates the worst-case loss scenario a trader would have experienced.

This multi-dimensional evaluation provides a more holistic and academically sound assessment of the strategy's efficiency, moving beyond a simple return calculation to incorporate considerations of risk management and capital preservation.

3.4 Transaction Costs and Charges in NEPSE

In the real-world simulation, to ensure realistic evaluation of trading strategies, all relevant transaction costs and regulatory charges applicable in the Nepal Stock Exchange (NEPSE) were incorporated into the model. The total cost per trade consists of four main components: broker commission, SEBON regularity fee, depository participant (DP) charge, and capital gains tax.

The broker commission is applied on both buy and sell transactions, with rates determined by the total transaction amount. The rate structure ranges from 0.36% (or a flat Rs. 10, whichever is higher) for transactions up to Rs. 50,000, gradually decreasing to 0.24% for transactions above Rs. 1 crore.

The SEBON regularity fee is charged at a constant rate of 0.015% of the transaction amount on both buy and sell sides, irrespective of the trade size.

The DP charge represents a fixed cost of Rs. 25 per sell transaction, applied once at the time of sale.

Finally, the capital gains tax is imposed only when a profit is realized upon sale of the security. The rate depends on the holding period: 7.5% of the profit amount for securities held less than one year (252 trading days), and 5% for those held one year or longer.

All of these costs were systematically modeled for each trade within the algorithmic framework. For the buy-and-hold strategy, charges were applied only upon the final sale transaction at the end of the investment horizon.

4 Parameter Optimization

4.1 Objective Function Optimization:

To identify the most effective lookback periods for each MA and also the best MA to use, an optimization process was performed. The objective function for this optimization is to maximize the Sharpe Ratio (SR). While simple net profit is valid metric, maximizing the Sharpe Ratio is a superior objective as it seeks to find the highest risk-adjusted return, which is a more robust indicator of a strategy's true performance.

The optimization of lookback periods (n_1 and n_2) was conducted using an exhaustive grid search over candidate short window lengths (n_1) and long window lengths (n_2). Subsequently, the pair that maximized the risk-adjusted performance metric (Sharpe Ratio) was selected.

Given a universe of stocks S , for each candidate pair (n_1, n_2), we simulated the Moving Average (MA) crossover strategy for each symbol $s \in S$ using the short window n_1 and the long window n_2 .

A long trade is entered when $SMA_{n_1} > SMA_{n_2}$, and exited when $SMA_{n_1} \leq SMA_{n_2}$. Trades are entered and exited at closing prices, and returns are recorded on the exit day.

For each symbol, we computed the trade-based daily-return series $r_t^{(s)}$, where non-exit days have a value of zero and exit days contain the realized trade return as a decimal. Then, we computed the Sharpe Ratio (SR) for each symbol s as follows:

$$SR^{(s)} = \frac{\bar{r}^{(s)}}{\sigma^{(s)}} \sqrt{N}$$

where:

- $\bar{r}^{(s)} = \text{mean}(r_t^{(s)})$ is the mean daily return,
- $\sigma^{(s)}$ is the population standard deviation of $r_t^{(s)}$
- $N = 252$ is the annualization factor.

If $\sigma^{(s)} = 0$, then $SR^{(s)}$ is undefined, and the symbol is excluded from averaging.

Finally, symbol-level Sharpe values were aggregated to obtain a single score for each parameter pair (n_1, n_2) as:

$$\text{Score}(n_1, n_2) = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{s \in S} SR^{(s)}$$

The optimal pair (n_1^*, n_2^*) was selected by:

$$(n_1^*, n_2^*) = \arg \max_{(n_1 < n_2)} \text{Score}(n_1, n_2)$$

Grid search is conceptually simple, fully deterministic, and exhaustively evaluates parameter combinations within a user-specified region. For two integer hyperparameters with modest ranges (e.g., a few dozen values each), grid search is computationally practical and produces a complete performance surface that is easy to inspect, visualize, and report.

This transparency is helpful for reproducibility and for diagnosing parameter sensitivity.

4.1.1 Boundary Conditions and Constraints:

- $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ (integer day lengths only)
- $n_1 < n_2$ (combinations violating this rule are skipped)

4.1.2 Search Setup:

Initial Coarse Grid Search

Short window: $n_1 \in \{5, 10, 15, \dots, 100\}$

Long window: $n_2 \in \{21, 31, 41, \dots, 200\}$

Step size: 10

Final Fine Grid Search

Short window: $n_1 \in \{5, 6, 7, \dots, 19\}$

Long window: $n_2 \in \{21, 22, 23, \dots, 39\}$

Step size: 1

4.1.3 Cross-Universal Validation Protocol

For empirical validation, we adopted a strict cross-universal train / out-of-sample (OOS) protocol to eliminate look-ahead bias and information leakage. Rather than splitting each symbol's time series into training and testing slices, we partitioned the universe of stocks:

- 80% of the symbols were used exclusively for parameter selection (training)
- The remaining 20% were reserved for out-of-sample testing and were never used during optimization

The training stage performed the exhaustive grid search and selected the parameter pair that maximized the Sharpe Ratio on the training universe. The selected configuration was then evaluated only once on the held-out 20% test universe. All performance metrics on this set were computed without any further fitting. This cross-universal split prevents temporal leakage, preserves the natural time structure of each series, and produces conservative and reproducible estimates of true out-of-sample performance.

5 Results and Discussions

5.1 Preliminary ADF Test Results

Table 2 shows the results of the preliminary ADF test of stationarity conducted on the NEPSE listed sectors (excluding mutual fund and debentures as they aren't as volatile and of interest of trading to like other sectors). It is observed that none of the stocks are stationary in nature which aligns with the findings from a recent study on weak form market inefficiency in NEPSE by Khanal et al. (Khanal, Thapa, & Bhandari, 2025). These findings support the possibility of a profitable trading strategy that can exploit past price to predict the future ones.

Table 2: ADF test of stationarity on sectors

Sector	p-value	Stationary?
BANKING	0.307067	No
DEVBANK	0.942336	No
FINANCE	0.758007	No
HOTELS	0.917614	No
HYDROPOWER	0.511414	No
INVESTMENT	0.489878	No
LIFEINSU	0.402502	No
MANUFACTURE	0.761323	No
MICROFINANCE	0.642419	No
NEPSE	0.913335	No
NONLIFEINSU	0.553866	No
OTHERS	0.860268	No
TRADING	0.710289	No

Note. The significant p-value threshold is set at 0.05.

5.2 Optimization of the Lookback Periods of Standard MAs

The lookback periods (n_1 and n_2) were optimized as explained in section 4.1 for all the MAs. The optimization process was carried out separately yielding varying optimized values for each of the stock category. This variance reflects the difference in momentum in low, mid and large cap companies. The optimized values for the lookback periods are given in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Optimized Values for n_1 and n_2

Moving Average	High Cap		Mid Cap		Low Cap	
	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2	n_1	n_2
SMA	6	21	15	21	11	21
EMA	5	21	6	21	11	21
TSEMA	5	21	5	21	5	21

Note. Table 3 shows the optimized values of n_1 and n_2 , obtained using historical prices of numerous stocks in each category. The range of n_1 is $5 \leq n_1 \leq 20$ and the range of n_2 is $21 \leq n_2 \leq 100$.

The results indicate a clear and consistent pattern in the optimized long-term parameter. Across all stock categories and all three moving averages, the long-term lookback period was optimized at 21 days. This finding implies that a 21-day (approximately one trading month) period effectively captures the medium-term market behaviour of the stocks in NEPSE, serving as a reliable indicator of trend direction and momentum persistence.

In contrast, the short-term lookback period (n_1) exhibited notable variations across capitalization levels and moving average types. For high-cap stocks, the optimal n_1 values ranged between 5 and 6, reflecting their lower volatility and smoother price trajectories. Mid-cap stocks required relatively longer short-term windows, $n_1 = 15$ for SMA and $n_1 = 6$ for EMA—indicating moderately volatile price behavior that benefits from additional smoothing. Low-cap stocks, on the other hand, showed $n_1 = 11$ for EMA and $n_1 = 5$ for TSEMA, suggesting that optimal responsiveness depends on the averaging method used.

A comparative assessment of the three moving averages reveals that exponential-based models (EMA and TSEMA) outperform the SMA in terms of adaptability to price fluctuations. The EMA and TSEMA display highly similar optimal parameters (both employing $n_1 = 5$ and $n_2 = 21$ for high and mid-cap stocks), indicating that higher-order smoothing in TSEMA provides only marginal improvement over the conventional EMA in the NEPSE context. Conversely, SMA consistently demands longer short-term periods, highlighting its slower adjustment to new price information due to equal weighting of past data points.

Overall, these results suggest that a 21-day long-term window coupled with a short-term window of 5–6 days offers an efficient configuration for identifying trend shifts in NEPSE equities. The results also emphasize that market capitalization significantly influences optimal lookback sensitivity as larger firms respond best to shorter horizons, while smaller and more volatile firms require longer or method-dependent smoothing to mitigate noise.

These findings carry important implications for technical traders and analysts. The consistency of the 21-day parameter implies a structural rhythm in the Nepalese equity market, likely tied to behavioural and institutional trading cycles. Meanwhile, the flexibility of exponential-based averages makes them particularly suitable for short to medium term momentum strategies.

5.3 Performance of the MA Algorithms (Ideal Condition):

After the optimization of the lookback periods and the weights (for NCMA), the algorithm is run on an out of sample dataset to figure out the profitability of the algorithms and find the relatively best performing one. Buy and Hold strategy is also included in the result table, which is our reference value to beat.

Table 4: Performance Analysis of the MA Algorithms (Ideal World Condition)

Moving Averages	High Cap	Mid Cap	Low Cap	Relative Rank
<i>In Terms of Average Profit %</i>				
SMA	193.729238%	132.220611%	140.580716%	4
EMA	281.175185%	184.793606%	305.058934%	3
TSEMA	238.979987%	238.226234%	404.994482%	1
Buy & Hold	693.119496%	213.648778%	290.854301%	2
<i>In Terms of Average Sharpe</i>				
SMA	0.369192	0.376444	0.469118	4
EMA	0.650664	0.351820	0.544678	2
TSEMA	0.552285	0.128466	0.494406	3
Buy & Hold	0.978212	0.385918	0.787583	1
<i>In Terms of Max Drawdown</i>				
SMA	22.499931%	19.798983%	25.231429%	2
EMA	22.924128%	16.335220%	26.118795%	1
TSEMA	28.738577%	27.134421%	31.367713%	3
Buy & Hold	51.785763%	49.946272%	60.073839%	4
<i>In Terms of Average Number of Trades</i>				
SMA	47.625000	29.954545	28.736842	3
EMA	49.000000	28.272727	21.526316	2
TSEMA	20.875000	13.590909	13.368421	1

Note. The explanations of each of the performance metrics are provided in Section 3.3. For the first two metrics, higher values indicate better performance, while for the third and fourth metrics, lower values are preferred. All reported values represent the arithmetic mean of the corresponding out-of-sample results for all stocks in each category.

In terms of average profit percentage, the TSEMA outperformed all other algorithms across most categories, achieving particularly strong results in low-cap stocks (404.99%). EMA performed well in high- and mid-cap stocks (281.18% and 184.79%, respectively), while SMA lagged behind due to slower adjustment to new price information. The Buy and Hold strategy, while yielding the highest absolute return for high-cap stocks (693.12%), which can be attributed to the fact that high cap NEPSE stocks were listed at severely undervalued prices during the starting years of NEPWSE, also involved greater exposure to drawdowns.

Regarding the Sharpe ratio, which measures risk-adjusted performance, the Buy and Hold strategy ranked first across most categories, with TSEMA and EMA performing competitively in low- and high-cap segments, respectively. SMA consistently recorded the lowest Sharpe ratios, reinforcing its limited adaptability to volatility.

When considering maximum drawdown, both EMA and SMA demonstrated lower drawdowns compared to Buy and Hold, suggesting better downside risk control. EMA achieved the lowest drawdowns overall (22.92% for high-cap and 16.33% for mid-cap stocks), indicating effective volatility smoothing.

In terms of average number of trades, EMA and SMA generated more frequent signals, while TSEMA exhibited fewer trades due to its higher smoothing strength. This lower trading frequency may translate to reduced transaction costs, making TSEMA advantageous for practical trading implementations.

Overall, the findings reveal a clear trade-off between responsiveness and stability among moving average strategies. TSEMA offers superior profitability with fewer trades, especially for low-cap stocks. EMA provides a balanced performance with high adaptability and lower risk. SMA is conservative but underperforms in dynamic market conditions. Buy and Hold, despite its high absolute return, suffers from significant drawdowns and volatility exposure. These results collectively indicate that moving average-based trading strategies particularly exponential models can outperform traditional Buy and Hold strategies in risk-adjusted terms under certain ideal brokerage free market conditions in NEPSE. The consistency of the 21-day long-term parameter and the efficiency of exponential smoothing methods highlight key behavioural patterns and potential inefficiencies in the Nepalese equity market that technical traders can systematically exploit. However, for some unknown reason, mid-cap sectors seem to generate the lowest Sharpe ratio and lowest max-drawdown which can be of great interest for further studies.

5.4 Performance of the MA Algorithms (Real Condition):

Table 5 and 6 show the performance of the algorithm in a real-world condition where it undergoes various transaction costs. In table 5, the capital is set as Rs.50,000 which incurs the highest broker commission. Meanwhile in table 6, the capital is set as Rs.1crore which incurs the least broker commission.

Table 5: Performance Analysis of the MA Algorithms (Real World Condition) (capital = Rs.50,000)

Moving Averages	High Cap	Mid Cap	Low Cap	Relative Rank
<i>In Terms of Average Profit %</i>				
SMA	134.367785%	94.820958%	100.793429%	4
EMA	213.516194%	144.349052%	258.240961%	3
TSEMA	199.409859%	206.355000%	363.826974%	1
Buy & Hold	591.046326%	200.622878%	234.979175%	2
<i>In Terms of Average Sharpe</i>				
SMA	0.201846	0.139206	0.313825	4
EMA	0.518526	0.203793	0.463432	1
TSEMA	0.483842	0.311000	0.438328	2
Buy & Hold	0.475785	0.121384	0.369963	3

Note. The explanations of each performance metric are given in Section 3.3, and transaction cost assumptions are detailed in Section 3.4. For all metrics, higher values indicate better performance. All results represent arithmetic means of the out-of-sample stock-level metrics for each category.

When transaction costs and taxes defined in Section 3.4 were incorporated, the overall profitability and performance of all moving average (MA) algorithms decreased significantly compared to the ideal condition (Section 5.3). This decline reflects the impact of brokerage commissions, SEBON fees, DP charges, and capital gains tax, which collectively reduce the net returns of frequent-trading strategies.

In terms of average profit percentage, the general ranking among strategies remained consistent with the ideal scenario, but the magnitude of returns declined. TSEMA continued to outperform other algorithms, particularly in the low-cap category (363.82%), followed by EMA (258.24%). The Buy and Hold strategy still exhibited the highest absolute returns in high-cap stocks (591.04%), but its relative advantage narrowed compared to the ideal condition. SMA again performed the weakest overall, confirming its inefficiency in adapting to price momentum even under real-world frictions.

The Sharpe ratios show a more distinct shift under real-world conditions. EMA emerged as the top performer (Sharpe ratios of 0.5185, 0.2038, and 0.4634 across high, mid, and low-cap stocks), surpassing TSEMA. This indicates that EMA's moderate trading frequency and smoother reaction to price changes provided superior risk-adjusted returns once trading costs were factored in. TSEMA, despite maintaining strong profitability, saw its relative Sharpe performance diminish slightly due to the higher costs associated with its occasional but high-profit trades. On the other hand, Buy and Hold had a high decrease in its sharpe ratio placing it just above SMA.

Overall, the introduction of transaction costs amplified the trade-off between profitability and trading frequency. Algorithms that generated excessive trade signals suffered proportionally higher cumulative costs, whereas smoother algorithms like TSEMA and EMA maintained robustness. TSEMA's lower trading frequency (as observed in Section 5.3) continues to serve as a practical advantage in cost-laden markets, making it well-suited for small-cap and low-liquidity stocks where costs erode returns quickly. Conversely, SMA's frequent trading and lagged responsiveness made it particularly vulnerable to cost inefficiencies.

These results underscore that while moving average strategies can outperform Buy and Hold on a risk-adjusted basis, their real-world profitability is highly sensitive to transaction costs and taxation structures. The consistency of TSEMA and EMA across both ideal and real-world scenarios highlights their adaptability and efficiency in the NEPSE environment. Meanwhile, the continued underperformance of SMA across all conditions confirms its limited utility in the volatile and cost-intensive context of emerging markets like Nepal.

Table 6: Performance Analysis of the MA Algorithms (Real World Condition) (capital = Rs.1,00,00,000)

Moving Averages	High Cap	Mid Cap	Low Cap	Relative Rank
<i>In Terms of Average Profit %</i>				
SMA	145.393617%	101.692869%	107.371445%	4
EMA	224.910679%	150.909793%	263.319072%	3
TSEMA	204.341993%	209.936000%	367.042087%	1
Buy & Hold	591.720449%	200.932668%	235.317840%	2
<i>In Terms of Average Sharpe</i>				
SMA	0.242708	0.200788	0.347269	4
EMA	0.550231	0.241751	0.479779	1
TSEMA	0.498387	0.320000	0.448811	2
Buy & Hold	0.475785	0.121384	0.369963	3

Note. The explanations of each performance metric are given in Section 3.3, and transaction cost assumptions are detailed in Section 3.4. For all metrics, higher values indicate better performance. All results represent arithmetic means of the out-of-sample stock-level metrics for each category.

With the higher capital in table 6, TSEMA continues to deliver the highest profitability among the MA algorithms across all stock categories, particularly in low-cap stocks, achieving a return of 367.04%. EMA follows, with notable performance in high-cap (224.91%) and low-cap (263.32%) stocks. SMA remains the least profitable algorithm overall, confirming its lag in adapting to price momentum even under reduced trading frictions. The Buy and Hold strategy maintains the highest absolute returns in high-cap stocks (591.72%), but its advantage over TSEMA and EMA narrows compared to smaller capital scenarios.

Compared to the Rs. 50,000 capital scenario (Table 5), both average profits and Sharpe ratios are higher across all strategies. This improvement is primarily due to the lower proportional brokerage and transaction costs for larger capital, which reduce the cost drag on frequent trades and enhance net returns. Strategies that involve more frequent trading, such as EMA and TSEMA, benefit particularly from this effect, translating into higher risk-adjusted performance.

EMA emerges as the top performer in terms of risk-adjusted returns, achieving Sharpe ratios of 0.5502, 0.2418, and 0.4798 across high, mid, and low-cap stocks, respectively. TSEMA ranks second, benefiting from its low trading frequency and the lower transaction costs, which improve net profitability per trade. Buy and Hold ranks third, reflecting its high absolute returns but continued vulnerability to volatility. SMA remains the least efficient, with Sharpe ratios below all other strategies in all categories.

The results highlight the trade-off between trading frequency, profitability, and risk-adjusted returns. TSEMA's lower number of trades continues to provide a practical advantage, particularly in low-cap and less liquid stocks where transaction costs can erode returns quickly. EMA's moderate responsiveness balances capturing price trends and minimizing excessive trades, which explains its superior Sharpe ratios under real-world conditions. SMA's conservative approach, characterized by slower adjustment to price changes, results in both lower profitability and risk-adjusted performance.

Overall, the higher capital base reduces the relative impact of brokerage, enhancing both profit and Sharpe ratios for all MA strategies compared to the smaller capital scenario. This demonstrates the sensitivity of trading strategy performance to transaction costs and highlights the advantage of using smoother, lower-frequency strategies like TSEMA and EMA in cost-intensive markets like NEPSE.

6 Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of moving average (MA) crossover strategies in the Nepal Stock Exchange (NEPSE), focusing on Simple (SMA), Exponential (EMA), and Triple Smoothed Exponential (TSEMA) moving averages. By analyzing historical stock data across high, mid, and low-cap stocks, and incorporating both idealized and real-world trading conditions (including transaction costs, taxes, and brokerage), the research offers insights into strategy performance, risk management, and practical applicability in an emerging market context.

The parameter optimization process revealed that a 21-day long-term window (n_2) consistently captures medium-term trends across all stock categories, highlighting a structural rhythm in NEPSE stocks likely tied to behavioral and

institutional trading cycles. Short-term windows (n_1) varied by stock capitalization and MA type, reflecting differences in volatility and price responsiveness. High-cap stocks favored shorter n_1 values (5–6 days), whereas mid- and low-cap stocks required longer or method-dependent smoothing to filter market noise effectively.

Under ideal conditions without transaction costs, TSEMA exhibited the highest profitability, especially in low-cap stocks, while EMA provided a balanced performance across high- and mid-cap segments. SMA consistently underperformed due to its slower responsiveness to price changes. The Buy-and-Hold strategy achieved the highest absolute returns for high-cap stocks but incurred significantly higher drawdowns and volatility exposure, indicating its lower risk-adjusted efficiency.

When real-world trading costs were incorporated, the performance of all strategies decreased, particularly for smaller capital amounts where brokerage and transaction fees represented a larger proportion of total trade value. With larger capital (Rs. 1 crore), the relative impact of transaction costs diminished, leading to higher net profitability and improved Sharpe ratios across all strategies. EMA emerged as the most effective risk-adjusted strategy in real-world conditions, benefiting from moderate trading frequency and responsiveness, while TSEMA maintained strong absolute profits with fewer trades, underscoring its practical advantage in low-liquidity and cost-intensive environments. SMA remained the least efficient across all scenarios.

The findings highlight several important insights:

- Trade-off between frequency and cost: Strategies with higher trading frequency can capture price trends effectively but are more sensitive to transaction costs, whereas smoother strategies achieve robust returns with lower operational costs.
- Market capitalization sensitivity: Optimal short-term lookback periods and strategy performance vary across high-, mid-, and low-cap stocks, emphasizing the need for capitalization-aware strategy design.
- Risk-adjusted performance superiority of exponential models: EMA and TSEMA outperform SMA and Buy-and-Hold on a risk-adjusted basis, demonstrating the effectiveness of exponential smoothing in capturing momentum while managing downside risk.
- Practical implications for traders: Technical traders in NEPSE can exploit structural patterns and inefficiencies using exponential-based MAs, particularly in low- to mid-cap stocks, while carefully considering trading costs and capital allocation.

Overall, this research demonstrates that MA crossover strategies, when properly parameterized and adjusted for real-world trading frictions, can provide systematic, risk-aware approaches to trading in the Nepalese equity market. Future studies may extend this work by incorporating additional technical indicators, multi-factor models, or intraday data to further enhance predictive power and robustness. The results also underscore the broader applicability of MA-based strategies in other emerging markets with similar structural and liquidity characteristics.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: JM, BD; methodology: JM; software: SA; validation: JM, SA, BD; formal analysis: JM; investigation: JM; resources: JM; data curation: SA; writing (original draft preparation): JM; writing (review and editing): JM, BD; visualization: JM; supervision: BD; project administration: JM. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability Statement

The main data source for this study is the Sharehub Api which can be accessed online at: <https://sharehubnepal.com/data/api/v1/candle-chart/history?symbol=CIT&resolution=1D&countback=0&isAdjust=true>. The refined dataset and used code will be available upon request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

AI Use Statement

The authors of the study confirm that the idea and content of this study aren't AI generated and no generative AI was used to generate the data. However, the authors acknowledge using ChatGPT to refine the coherence of ideas and grammar.

References

References

- [1] Anghel, D. G. (2013). How Reliable Is the Moving Average Crossover Rule for an Investor on the Romanian Stock Market? *The Review of Finance and Banking*, 5(2), 089-115. Retrieved from <https://www.cceol.com/search/article-detail?id=848676>
- [2] de Souza, M., Ramos, D., Pena, M., Sobreiro, V., & Kimura, H. (2018, February 24). Examination of the profitability of technical analysis based on moving average strategies in BRICS. *Financial Innovation*, 4(1), 3. doi:10.1186/s40854-018-0087-z
- [3] Ikhlās, G. (2016, March). The Moving Average Crossover Strategy: Does It Work for the S&P500 Market Index? *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 7(1), 92-107. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2578302>
- [4] Khanal, M., Thapa, B., & Bhandari, M. (2025, January 20). Weak Form of Market Efficiency in Nepalese Stock Market. *Journal of Business and Econometrics Studies*, 2(1), 1-10.
- [5] Risal, H., & Koju, P. (2021). Testing the weak form of efficiency in Nepalese stock markets. *SEBON Journal*, 8(1), 20-33.
- [6] Tapa, A., Yean, S. C., & Ahmad, S. N. (2016). Modified Moving-average Crossover Trading Strategy: Evidence in Malaysia Equity Market. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 6(7), 149-153. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ijefi/issue/32000/353047>